

Environmental enrichment for ruminants and equines

What is an enrichment?

The concept of environmental enrichment refers to a wide range of modifications to the environment of captive or farmed animals that offer adequate stimulation and facilitate the expression of highly motivated behaviour thus promoting positive emotions and improving the animal's welfare. Environmental enrichments can be classified into five (non-exclusive) categories:

- Physical enrichments that include the complexity of the animal's enclosure and the provision of additional elements (e.g. hiding places);
- Occupational enrichments that promote physical and/or psychological activities by providing opportunities to exercise or to engage in cognitive tasks;
- Sensory enrichments, designed to stimulate one or several senses of the animal;
- Feeding enrichments that promote foraging and feeding behaviour by providing new or varied foods, or feed delivery methods or tools;
- Relational enrichments that embrace social contacts, and specific bonds with conspecifics or individuals of other species (including humans).

Further information is provided in the **Thematic factsheet 'Environmental enrichment for ruminants and equines: the basics'**.

Legal requirements

The EU legislation to protect farm ruminants and equines does not mention enrichment. Council Directive 98/58/EC for the protection of farmed animals nevertheless mentions ethological (behavioural) needs. Council Directive 2008/119/EC specifies that calves

must have visual and tactile contacts and must be kept in group from the age of 8 weeks.

Council Directive 2010/63/EU for the protection of animals used for scientific purposes mentions enrichment, in reference to behavioural expression and stress reduction.

Method

To assess whether enrichment is appropriately provided to animals, it is essential to consider species-specific needs and their living environment. For examples of enrichments and their expected impact on the welfare of different species, see **Thematic factsheets 'Environmental enrichment for cattle', 'Environmental enrichment for sheep', 'Environmental enrichment for goats', and 'Environmental enrichment for equines'**.

Enrichment is only considered to be enriching if it is perceived as such by the animal, i.e. providing opportunities to fulfill behavioural needs and experience positive emotions and good welfare. Housing supplementations (i.e. adding a few elements to suboptimal environments) that decrease poor welfare in the short term but are not sufficient to promote good welfare are thus not considered as enrichment.

Giving access to a variety of enrichments in place and over time (i.e. increasing the complexity of the environment and exposing animals to changing environments) while avoiding overstimulation, and allowing animals to behave as an active agent in their environment (i.e. allowing choice between items used for enrichment and control over situations) is generally highly valued by animals.

Recommendation for inspection

See species-specific factsheets on cattle, sheep, goats and equines for further details

During the inspection, the following check points should be considered:

- 1. What enrichments are present?**
Assess the types of enrichment, their quantity and apparent appropriateness.
- 2. Are the enrichments used by animals?**
Assess the proportion of animals using enrichments or waiting to use them; look for signs of use (object bitten, brushes with signs of wear).
- 3. Do enrichments engage animals over long periods?**
Assess if enrichments are diverse and variable in time, if animals can choose between enrichments, if they can control the use of an enrichment.
- 4. Are there behavioural signs of poor and/or good welfare?**
Assess behavioural signs of positive emotions (e.g. exploration, play in young animals, resting) vs. negative emotions (e.g. stereotypies, aggression, hyper-reactivity); look for the presence of any injuries that may have been caused by an inappropriate enrichment.

Example of the use of the above four check points applied to three enrichments on a dairy farm:

1	Physical, occupational and feeding enrichment 1 outdoor area of 500 m ² for 50 cows		
2	40% of the cows outside during daytime		
3	Cows: varied environment with choice and control (e.g. free access day and night to outdoor, free use of the brush in a pathway)		
4	Cows: signs of positive emotions (exploration, self-grooming, allogrooming) and very few lame cows and head butts. However, competition to access the brush		